

PROFESIO EXPERIENCES

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ISBN ASSIGNMENT PROCESS IN MOLDOVA

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Abstracts: This article describes how the publisher can apply for and obtain ISBN for publications that are within the scope of the ISBN Standard, the procedures the publisher must to follow and the legal framework that regulates publishing activity in the Republic of Moldova.

Keywords: National Book Chamber of the Republic of Moldova, NBCRM, ISBN assignment, ISBN National Agency, ISO standard

National Book Chamber of the Republic of Moldova (NBCRM)¹³ was designated as ISBN National Agency in 1993, when Republic of Moldova becomes a member of ISBN network.

The operating rules of the ISBN System in the Republic of Moldova¹⁴ were developed based on the Editorial Activity Law Nr 939/2000 with subsequent modifications and additions, the policy and strategy of the International ISBN Agency, which establishes how to manage the ISBN system, and the management of the National ISBN Registry of the Republic of Moldova.

The ISBN information system in the Republic of Moldova is intended for the registration of ISBN numbers assigned to books and brochures published by Moldova's publishers, printed in the country, and abroad.

The ISBN numbers are assigned by the NBC as the ISBN Moldova National Agency and are based on the ISO 2108:2017 "Information and Documentation - International Standard Book Number (ISBN)".

The ISBN system in the Republic of Moldova with the NBC as the ISBN Moldova National Agency is operated according to the Republic of Moldova legislation and the relevant international standard in the field (ISO 2108).

ISBNs are intended for publishers who operate in the Republic of Moldova and have completed their registration at the NBC.

ISBN assignment is chargeable according to the Payments Service Nomenclature approved by the Government Decision Nr 1311 of 12.12.2005.

In 2006, ISBN National Agency Moldova started to use the 13-digit ISBN system. In the same period, Moldova's ISBN database was established with full data records regarding publishers, contacts, ISBNs, and complete data about registered titles.

"Moldova's ISBN" database, front office

Titlu	ISBN														
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In accordance with the Republic of Moldova's laws to become a publisher, each legal entity must meet these requirements:

1. the legal status must include the economic classification of activity - "58.11 book publishing activities" or "18.1 printing and printing related service activities" according to NACE rev. 2 (Classification of Economic Activities in EC)¹⁵
2. to sign a contract between the legal entity and National Book Chamber of Republic of Moldova.

13 Conference "Contemporary use, models and allocation of ISBN across of World"
14 <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=358447>

15 <http://www.statistica.md/pageview.php?l=en&idc=385>

The National Book Chamber of Moldova is also designated as CIP agency and National Bibliographic Agency. Therefore, every publisher, upon his request to register a new title, will get the CIP, UDC, and ISBN. In Moldova, the process of obtaining the ISBN follows the model "one request - one allocated ISBN".

Upon registration, publishers receive an ISBN for each title, regardless of the number of titles / documents received each day. Publishers can apply for subsequent ISBNs through the (mandatory) confirmation of previously requested ISBNs, as required by law.

There are two ways to make a request – either in person at the NBC office or online (via email). The first variant permits two methods of payment – by cash at the NBC office or by bank transfer, the second permits just one – the bank transfer.

Registration at the NBC office

Online registration via email

Providing a Legal Deposit copy is mandatory and this must be presented to NBC and submitted within two months (for titles that will be printed out of the country the deadline will be extended) of assignment of the ISBN number. At the back office of the "Moldova's ISBN" database, we have full data records of all registered titles, with blue is marked titles that NBC has not yet received as Legal Deposit.

"Moldova's ISBN" database, back office for ISBN prefixes "978-9975-0"

Inventar	Data	ISBN-13	Autor	Tipografia	Tiraj
	26.12.2017	978-9975-0-0114-4	Santilian Jorge	Coloarea anuale - P. 1	Malaysa 2000
	26.12.2017	978-9975-0-0115-1	Santilian Jorge	Coloarea anuale - P. 2	Malaysa 3000
2017-2663	02.01.2018	978-9975-0-0116-8	Răpopanu Veronica	Limba română pentru școlile cu instruire în limba rusă - clasa a 9-a - Căsuța elevului	Bons Offices 2000
2018-174	02.01.2018	978-9975-0-0117-5	Грегорь Мигуя	В помощь у Мадоннона Мирам - (обзорник терапевтических навыков для детей дошкольного и младшего школьного возраста), ed. 2	Bons Offices 1000
	11.01.2018	978-9975-0-0118-2		Obște și contribuție - Carte a urubii de conștient	China 1000
2018-366	23.01.2018	978-9975-0-0119-9	Ursu Valeriu	Jurnal săptămânal la Europa Liberă / Parla a 13-a - dec. 2016 - dec. 2017	Bons Offices 1200
2018-360	29.01.2018	978-9975-0-0120-5	Vandabiri Michael	New rom antics	Bons Offices 500
2018-784	02.02.2018	978-9975-0-0121-2	Myajlin Jan in	Posole, poezii și jurnale / Cincisprezece poezii neerlandezi	Bons Offices 600
2018-782	12.02.2018	978-9975-0-0122-9	Steele Philip	Abstrul meu geografic - contine un poster pliat cu harta lumii	China 2000
2018-400	14.02.2018	978-9975-0-0123-6	Enicu Nicolae	1918 pe ruinele imperiului srbobater de sitone. Basarabia în pragul modernității	Bons Offices 300
2018-363	14.02.2018	978-9975-0-0124-3	Turcanu Ion	Săptămîna întoarsă la unel importante instituții politice basarabene din anii 1917-1918	Bons Offices 300
2018-676	20.02.2018	978-9975-0-0125-0	Bulac Vladimir	Forme geometrice - Un eseu despre artelul Dumtru Russu. Scenariul gipsera sa	Bons Offices 500
	26.02.2018	978-9975-0-0126-7	Căpăanu Dragoș	Cartea mea de magie	China 2000
	26.02.2018	978-9975-0-0127-4	Sera	Biblioteca creativă	China 2000
2018-793	15.03.2018	978-9975-0-0128-1	Clușdaru Mihail Ion	Tenerea de dăburtă	Bons Offices 500
	16.03.2018	978-9975-0-0129-8	Secreanu Rodica	Republica Moldova. Cursul Constituțional. Raport privind exercitarea jurisdicției constituționale în anul 2017	Europes 200
	21.03.2018	978-9975-0-0130-4	Bulac Nicolae	De la genă la palet	Ungaria 1000
2018-794	29.03.2018	978-9975-0-0131-1	Mencu George	Pe rug facuta dintr-un liber	Bons Offices 500
	03.04.2018	978-9975-0-0132-8	Bucurari Claria	Fără țăriști: Cum să fi o țară în mod	Ungaria 4000
2018-793	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0133-5	Ungureanu Mihai	Să câștig părinți, să câștig copii - Culegere de clinice pentru toate vârstele	Bons Offices 1000
2018-638	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0134-2	Valeco Nadejda	China - Teste preparatori pentru examenul de bacalaureat (profil real, profilul umanistic, arti, sport)	Bons Offices 2000
2017-796	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0135-9	Величко Надежда	Химия - Тесты для подготовки к экзамену на степень бакалавра (профиль: реальный, гуманитарный, экономико-информационный)	Bons Offices 2000
	08.04.2018	978-9975-0-0136-6	Botnaru Vasile	Descalțarea pentru un Microantologie cu oenografie	Ungaria 1100
2018-799	11.04.2018	978-9975-0-0137-3	Lungu Svetlana	English-Speaking Countries - Culture and Civilization Topics for the Baccalaureate Exam	Bons Offices 3000
	24.04.2018	978-9975-0-0138-0	Lungu Eugen	Mihai Bacarici - Grădă de carte	Combinatul Poligrafic 500
	25.04.2018	978-9975-0-0139-7	Dugin Olivier	Itoriana povestite în 5 minute înainte de culcare	Ungaria 4000
	04.05.2018	978-9975-0-0140-3	Sera	Itoriana Bănuț	Ungaria 3000
	04.05.2018	978-9975-0-0141-0	Omuchoșkăne Răsa	Zua de naștere - 2+ - cu autocarante	Ungaria 3000
	04.05.2018	978-9975-0-0142-7	Omuchoșkăne Răsa	Zua mea - 2+ - cu autocarante	Ungaria 3000
	04.05.2018	978-9975-0-0143-4	Omuchoșkăne Răsa	O zi de naștere - 2+ - cu autocarante	Ungaria 3000
	06.05.2018	978-9975-0-0144-1	Omuchoșkăne Răsa	În pășuni - 2+ - cu autocarante	Ungaria 3000
	07.05.2018	978-9975-0-0145-8	Leonardi Harley Stefania	Cele mai frumoase povești clasice	China 3000

Thanks to this model of ISBN allocation, we have achieved outstanding results in the editorial-publishing field:

- The Legal Deposit in Moldova covers 98% of all published documents;
- The illegal use of ISBNs has been excluded (duplication, erroneous writing);
- Quick possibility of identifying the author-title-ISBN relationship;
- Exemption from VAT on the basis of the systematization certificate issued by the NBC.

References:

1. The Editorial Activity Law Nr 939-XIV from 20.04.2000 <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=341833>
2. The operating rules of the ISBN System in the Republic of Moldova <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=358447>
3. ISO 2108:2017 "Information and Documentation - International Standard Book Number (ISBN)" <http://www.iso.org/standard/65483.html>
4. The Fiscal code of the Republic of Moldova, Title III "Value Added Tax", art. 103 <http://lex.justice.md/md/32697/>